

Interview Questions

These 7 questions are a widely-used technique by government policy advisors to gain strategic insights from a range of internal and external stakeholders. These questions are used to structure a 60-minute long interview with individuals to identify strategic issues that will need to be addressed during the focus groups conducted later in the project.

The seven questions are below. Any additional questions that may be needed will be similar to these in order to gain more detail or insight into the issues that may be described.

Warm-up questions:

- Could you briefly tell us about your current role and how you connect with the aerospace sector?
 - Thinking about the Brundtland definition of sustainability, what connections do you see between sustainability and the aerospace sector?
1. What do you see as the main drivers for sustainability in the aerospace sector?
 2. If you could speak to a person from the future, for example 2050, who could tell you about a sustainable aerospace sector in Aotearoa New Zealand, what would you like to ask? What are the critical issues for the future?
 3. What would be a good outcome for a sustainable aerospace sector and what would be the signs for that?
 4. What would be a bad outcome for a sustainable aerospace sector and what would be the signs for that?
 5. Looking back over the last decade, what successes we can build on? What can we learn from any failures? (these could come from New Zealand or international examples)
 6. What needs to be done now to make sure we achieve a good outcome?
 7. If you had absolute authority or had a magic wand, and could do anything without any constraints, what more would you wish to see happen?